

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

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Storage Duration

Use Case

René Blanc is planning a study on stress-induced depression among nursing staff in dementia care. As part of the study, interviews with care staff are planned over a period of five years. They will be recorded using a recording device. In addition, the study participants will complete a questionnaire every year. While preparing the informed-consent document, René Blanc is confronted with the question of how long the collected data must be stored.

What are the legal requirements for retaining data?

For data covered by the Human Research Act, specific retention periods are regulated in the act's various ordinances. For other types of data, other laws governing the specific matter may apply, each of which may stipulate its own retention period. This must be examined on a case-by-case basis, and legal advice should be sought.

Do organizations that provide research funding, like the SNSF or universities, have any stipulations about data-retention periods?

In addition to legal regulations, a university or faculty may issue binding directives for employees on the retention period of research data, or organizations that provide research funding may specify a retention period. The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) takes into account the different practices of the various disciplines and does not prescribe a binding retention period, but it does recommend storing data for at least ten years.

What regulations are there regarding the deletion of data?

You must comply with the Data Protection Act when deleting personal data. In principle, personal data must be deleted if they are no longer required for the purpose for which they were collected. This does not apply if a law prohibits the deletion of the data or specifies certain retention periods. Moreover, both storage and deletion are considered data processing. This means that consent must also be obtained to delete data. The principal investigator is responsible for deleting data. In the case of clinical data, study participants must be informed that there is a legal obligation to retain the data.

What does that mean for this case?

For the data that René Blanc is collecting, there is no statutorily prescribed retention obligation.

Since the study participants have to be contacted several times during the course of the project, it is only possible to anonymize the data after the study has been completed. So René Blanc stores the data in a pseudonymized form during the project and informs the participants accordingly in the consent document. Pseudonymization provides additional protection to the study participants.

After the study has been completed, the data from the questionnaires are completely anonymized, and the original files are deleted. René Blanc also obtains consent to do this. It is impossible to anonymize the audio recordings completely, which is why these data are deleted after the study is complete and only the anonymized transcriptions are preserved. Following the recommendations of the SNSF, René Blanc stores these data on the university's servers for at least ten years. René Blanc also makes the data used for publications available on a repository.

To make sure that the data are correctly deleted, René Blanc seeks advice from IT services.